

The Effect of Price and Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions of Teh Hitam Celup Tambi (Study on Consumers of PT Perkebunan Tambi Wonosobo)

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ABSTRACT: PT Perkebunan Tambi is a tea company in Wonosobo district which produces various kinds of tea, one of which is the Tambi Black Tea. Based on sales data for Tambi Black Tea Dips from 2017 to 2021 sales of Tambi Dip Black Tea are very volatile, especially in 2020 it experienced a very drastic decline reaching -68.9% as a result of the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic. This study aims to prove the effect of price and product quality on purchasing decisions of Tambi Black Tea Celup in Wonosobo. This type of research is explanatory research with purposive sampling and accidental sampling techniques. Data collection used in this study by submitting questionnaires to respondents. The number of samples in this study amounted to 97 respondents in Wonosobo Regency who had bought or consumed Tambi Dip Black Tea. The data analysis method used was validity test, reliability test, correlation coefficient, determination coefficient test, simple regression analysis and multiple regression analysis, then significance test (t test and F test) using the SPSS for Windows version 25.0 program. The results of this study show that partially price contributes 25.7% and product quality 27.2% to purchasing decisions. Meanwhile, price and product quality simultaneously contributed 30.9% to purchasing decisions. Based on these results, it can be seen that the price partially has a significant negative effect on the purchasing decision variable. Product quality partially has a significant positive effect on purchasing decision variables. Price and product quality simultaneously have a significant influence on purchasing decision variables. Suggestions from this study are for companies to evaluate pricing and product packaging as well as procedures for presenting products so that they can attract consumers to purchase Tambi Celup Black Tea.

KEYWORDS: Price; Product Quality; Purchasing Decisions

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesian plantations are needed by the community in their daily lives as elements of basic needs and complementary needs. One of Indonesia's plantation crops is tea, where our people are very close to consuming tea. According to data from the Ministry of Agriculture, it was recorded that in 2020 the area of tea plantations in Indonesia reached 112,307 hectares, consisting of 38,332 hectares belonging to the Large State Plantations (PBN) and 22,740 hectares belonging to the Large Private Plantations (PBS), while 51,235 owned to the People's Plantations (PR). hectare. The data shows that many of our people still depend on the existence of tea plantations.

Tea brands in Indonesia are very diverse, spread throughout the archipelago, starting from Tambi Tea, Sariwangi Tea, Sosro Botol Tea, Dandang Tea and others. The product variations also vary in terms of packaging, price, aroma and product quality. Serving tea products also has many ways, some are directly drunk such as bottled tea and tea boxes, some are dyed or brewed. The researcher determines the Tambi Black Tea Products which are produced by PT. Tambi Wonosobo Plantation. This is because all types of Tambi tea have proven international standard quality and have been exported to several countries such as America, Britain, Iraq, Germany, Canada, New Zealand, United Arab Emirates, Egypt, Chile and Pakistan.

Tambi Celup Black Tea is one of the tea products in Indonesia and is very popular with the wider community. Tambi Black Tea has been produced by PT Perkebunan Tambi since 1957 in Wonosobo Regency which is divided into four units, namely the Directors' Office, the Tambi Plantation Unit, the Bedakah Plantation Unit, and the Tanjungsari Plantation Unit. PT Perkebunan Tambi produces two types of tea, namely black tea and green tea which are divided into various packages. The Tambi Black Tea Plant is located on the slopes of Mount Sindoro and Sumbing with an altitude of 4500 feet above sea level with rainfall of 2500 to 2000 s.d. 3,500 mm per year to produce quality plants.

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The advantage possessed by PT Perkebunan Tambi is that it has a strong history where the journey of the Tambi Black Tea Bag has been made since the Dutch colonial era and has passed through various generations and connoisseurs. Besides that, another advantage is that consumers already know the company and have high trust. The next advantage is having continuity because the Tambi Black Tea Celup product has a different taste supported by a good climate, good plants so as to produce a quality product.

The quality of products from PT Perkebunan Tambi also has a good standard and has fulfilled various trials. PT Perkebunan Tambi has received a HACCP (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point) certificate to ensure that Tambi Tea is a safe and internationally recognized food industry. In addition, PT Perkebunan Tambi also has RA (Rainforest Alliance) certification as support for harmony in growing between humans and nature. Tambi tea has also passed halal certification and BPOM tests as proof that the product is completely safe and halal for consumption. The series of trial tests is PT Perkebunan Tambi's step in maintaining product quality as stipulated by the government in the health, religious and trade sectors.

PT Perkebunan Tambi divides Tambi Tea products into three levels. The first level, namely Grade I tea with the highest quality, is the result of rolling it into the RRB (Rotary Roll Breaker) which produces product 1 with a smooth texture and a very dark black color. Grade II tea has tea quality below Grade I which does not pass the RRB I sieve and will then enter the milling machine/Rotor Vane (RV) which produces Grade II tea. Grade III tea is the lowest quality tea that does not pass the RRB II and RV II sieve and is then sifted using RRB III to produce Grade III tea powder.

Tambi Tea brands also vary according to quality and price. This difference is differentiated starting from the smallest quantity, namely the contents of 15 pcs, until it is sent to companies in thousands of kilos using sacks sent to national and international companies such as Unilever. One of the brands that is very popular with the public, namely Tambi Black Tea, the smallest type of tea bag. The Tambi Celup Black Tea product is a type of Tambi Celup Black Tea which is marketed to the local community. This type of tea can be purchased retail or wholesale with certain discounts if you buy certain quantities.

Table 1. Marketing Data of Teh Hitam Celup Tambi PT Perkebunan Tambi's (in one box)

YEAR	TOTAL BOX	PERCENTAGE INCREASE
2017	15.435	-
2018	17.233	11,6
2019	17.831	0,23
2020	5.531	-68,9
2021	10.766	-48,6
TOTAL	146.386	

Source : PT Perkebunan Tambi, 2022

Based on several theories, there are factors that influence the level of purchasing decisions for a product, one of which is the price and quality of the product. As is the case with PT Perkebunan Tambi in Wonosobo Regency, to attract consumers, companies must first be able to meet the needs and desires of consumers, such as price compatibility with product benefits. Besides that, it also has to improve product quality both in terms of taste, color, aroma and factors of product quality.

Tambi Black Tea Bags containing 15 pcs has a market share that is not too wide. Through interviews conducted by researchers to the marketing department of PT Perkebunan Tambi said that the Black Tea Celup Tambi has a middle to upper class share. Consumers of Tambi Black Tea Dip are popular with young tea connoisseurs at caffeshops where young people gather, besides that Tambi Dip Black Tea products are popular with tourists visiting Wonosobo Regency. Fans of Tambi Black Tea Dips, when viewed from a geographical location, are favored by residential communities or urban environments. Some places that are difficult to reach, such as in sub-districts in remote areas, cannot be reached by the company because of the high cost of transportation that does not match the demand.

There are several reasons that differentiate consumers of Tambi Black Tea Bags and consumers of Tambi Black Tea Bags in other packages, namely that connoisseurs of Tambi Black Tea Bags are no longer concerned with price but have a taste match because the ingredients of Tambi Black Tea Bags are from superior quality grade I leaves, namely PS type (Pecco Souchan) the highest leaf in the tea leaf structure. The quality of Tambi Black Tea is the same as the type marketed for the international market.

Researchers assume through the above data from the consumer's point of view that PT Perkebunan Tambi has four problems related to two factors, namely price and product quality which have an impact on reducing consumer purchasing

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decisions. This problem shows that there are consumer expectations that cannot be fulfilled by the company, causing dissatisfaction and the inability of consumers to purchase these products. These data indicate that companies must be able to meet the needs and desires of consumers to increase sales.

PT Perkebunan Tambi in increasing sales needs to pay attention to the suitability of price and product quality of the Tambi Black Tea Bag so that it can move consumers to make a purchasing decision. Consumers always want the minimum sacrifice but with the maximum possible benefits. One of the factors that consumers consider is affordability, where prices that match quality will create good consumer decisions. Product quality is also a consideration for consumers in purchasing decisions because good product quality will meet consumer expectations for the product purchased. Companies that create products at affordable prices and reliable quality will lead to consumer decisions that have an impact on increasing sales volume and generating maximum profits. Based on this explanation, the researcher determined the X1 variable, namely price, and the X2 variable, namely product quality.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Consumer behavior

According to James F. Engel (2016), consumer behavior is the actions of individuals who are directly involved in obtaining or using economic goods and services including the decision-making process that precedes and determines these actions. Consumer behavior can also be interpreted as the study of how individuals, groups, and organizations select, buy, use, and how goods, services, ideas, or experiences satisfy their needs or desires (Kotler and Keller, 2009).

B. Price

According to Phillip Kotler (2012) price is the amount of money consumers are willing to sacrifice for a product or service. The definition of the price of the product includes the cost of the product and all costs sacrificed starting from the purchase of materials, the process of becoming goods, until they are exchanged in the market. Prices are not just numbers on a label, they can take many forms and serve many functions. Rent, prices, fees, taxes, salaries, wages and commissions are all prices paid for goods or services.

Consumers in determining purchasing decisions based on price have several specific indicators. According to Phillip Kotler (2012: 314), price indicators consist of:

- a. Price affordability
Affordable prices are consumers' expectations before they make a purchase. Consumers will look for products whose prices they can afford.
- b. Compatibility of price with product quality
For certain products, consumers usually do not mind if they have to buy at relatively high prices as long as the quality of the product is good. However, consumers prefer products with low prices and good quality.
- c. Price competitiveness
The company determines the selling price of a product by considering the price of products sold by competitors so that its products can compete in the market.
- d. Price compatibility with benefits
The high and low prices must be in accordance with the benefits received by consumers after making a purchase.
- e. Price list
Price list is a description of the price listed on the label or product offered.
- f. Discount
Discount is a price reduction from the attached price list. There are four types of discounts, namely:
 1. Cash discount, which is a price reduction to buyers who pay their bills early.
 2. Quantity discount, is a price reduction for buyers who buy in large quantities.
 3. A functional discount (also known as a trade discount) is offered by the seller to trade channel members who perform certain functions such as selling, storing and reporting.
 4. Seasonal discount, is a price reduction for buyers who buy merchandise or services out of season
- g. Credit
Credit is a form of payment by way of a loan according to the agreed time.
- h. Payment period

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The payment period is installments according to the agreement between the seller and the buyer, usually related to credit. This period can be in the short term, medium term, and long term.

C. Product Quality

According to John W. Mullins and Orville C. Walker (2005) defines that a product is anything that fulfills a want or need through use, consumption or acquisition. Mullins (2005) also added that in order to maintain a competitive advantage in the market, companies must understand aspects of product quality dimensions, namely reliability, suitability, durability, design, service, and perceived quality.

According to Orville, Larreche, and Boyd (2005: 422) there are seven product quality indicators, namely:

1. Performance
Performance includes the main operational characteristics of the core product purchased. Operational characteristics such as comfort, convenience, speed and others.
2. Additional Facilities (Features)
Additional facilities are complementary facilities including facilities outside the main facilities of the product.
3. Reliability
Reliability, namely being able to believe that the product will satisfy and is less likely to be damaged even if it is not used for a certain period of time.
4. Conformance with specifications (Conformance to specifications)
Conformity specifications whether the design and operational characteristics have been met in accordance with the standards of view.
5. Durability
Durability is the length of time the product can be used properly, comfortably and safely.
6. Aesthetics (Aesthetic)
Aesthetics, namely the attractiveness of the product through the advantages that can be captured by the senses.
7. Perceived quality
The impression of quality is the result of using indirect measurements because there is a possibility that consumers do not understand or lack information about the product in question.

D. Buying Decision

Purchasing decisions are an integration process that is combined to evaluate two or more of several alternative behaviors and determine the choice of one of them as an option (Oslo and Peter, 2019: 162).

Spillane (1994) divides the facilities into facilities and infrastructure as follows:

Consumers decide to buy through various factors. According to Oslo and Peter (2019: 162) there are four indicators in purchasing decisions, namely:

- a. Convenience in buying
Stability in a product is a belief that consumers have in a product where consumers believe that the product will meet their needs.
- b. Considerations in buying
Considerations in buying, namely consumer perceptions to prefer the product compared to other brands.
- c. Price factor
Price is a material consideration for consumers in making purchasing decisions. Consumers will choose between prices that are suitable for choice.
- d. Compatibility of attributes with wants and needs
Compatibility of attributes with wants and needs, namely consumer perceptions of interest in the product compared to other brands because it fits their needs.

III. HYPOTHESIS

Based on theory and literature review, the following research hypotheses were formulated:

H1: It is suspected that there is a partial price effect on purchasing decisions

H2: It is suspected that there is a partial influence of Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions

H3: it is suspected that there is price and product quality simultaneously on purchasing decisions

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IV. METHOD

This study uses explanatory research with a quantitative approach. Explanatory research is research that is usually used to find out what happens and what influences it. Researchers have not only described the phenomenon that occurred but have tried to explain what influences the phenomenon to occur. This research focuses on the influence between the Price variable (X1) and the Product Quality variable (X2) on the Purchase Decision variable (Y). Price and Product Quality are the independent variables, the Purchase Decision variable is the dependent variable.

Determining the number of samples was carried out using non-probability sampling technique with a total of 97 respondents, then for the technique using accidental sampling, purposive sampling, and snowball sampling with the following criteria for respondents:

- The people of Wonosobo Regency or live in Wonosobo Regency
- Have purchased and consumed the Tambi Black Tea Celup product at least twice in the last three months
- Age 17 and over
- Willing to fill out a questionnaire related to this research.

V. RESULT

From the results of the collection that has been carried out, the following are the results of several analyzes including the correlation coefficient, determination coefficient, simple and multiple linear regression, and significance test to determine the effect of price and product quality on purchasing decision

Table 2. Price Correlation Test Results on Purchasing Decisions
Correlations

		Price (X1)	Purchasing Decisions (Y)
Price (X1)	Pearson Correlation	1	-.507**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000
	N	97	97
Purchasing Decisions (Y)	Pearson Correlation	-.507**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	
	N	97	97

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

The table above shows that the correlation coefficient (r) or the closeness between the price variable (X1) and the purchase decision (Y) is -0.507. The results of the correlation coefficient test show that the relationship between the price variable (X1) and the purchase decision (Y) is negative and significant. If you look at the r value interval table, the value of -0.507 is in the interval 0.400-0.599 which means the level of correlation is moderate.

Table 3. Product Quality Correlation Test Results On Purchasing Decisions
Correlations

		Product Quality	Purchasing Decisions
Product Quality (X2)	Pearson Correlation	1	.521**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000
	N	97	97
Purchasing Decisions (Y)	Pearson Correlation	.521**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	
	N	97	97

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

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The table above shows that the correlation coefficient or closeness between product quality variables (X2) and purchasing decisions (Y) is 0.521. The results of the correlation coefficient test show that the relationship between product quality variables (X2) and purchasing decisions (Y) is positive and significant. If you look at the r value interval table, the value of 0.521 is in the interval 0.400-0.599 which means the level of relationship is moderate.

Table 4. Simple Linear Regression Test Results of Price on Purchasing Decisions Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	35.700	1.204		29.644	.000
Price (X1)	-.382	.067	-.507	-5.727	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decisions (Y)

The results of the regression coefficient test on the price variable (X1) worth -0.382 have a positive value, so it can be assumed that the variable (X1) has a negative influence on the purchasing decision variable (Y). Through the coefficient table, a significance value of 0.000 is obtained which has a value below the probability of 0.05, so it can be concluded that the price variable (X1) influences the purchasing decision variable (Y). Based on the test results, it was found that the price variable (X1) influenced the purchase decision variable (Y) by -50.7%. So it can be concluded that if the price of the Tambi Black Tea Bag is more affordable and the suitability of the price with the quality of the product is met, the purchasing decisions made by consumers will also increase. The higher the price appraisal, the lower the purchase decision, conversely, the lower the price assessment, the higher the purchase decision.

Table 5. Simple Linear Regression Test Results for Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.759	2.229		7.071	.000
	Product Quality (X2)	.303	.051	.521	5.953	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decisions (Y)

Based on the test results, it was found that the product quality variable (X2) influenced the purchase decision variable (Y) by 52.1%. So that it can be concluded that if the price of the Tambi Black Tea Bag is more affordable and the suitability of the price with the quality of the product is met, the purchasing decisions made by consumers will also increase. The more the assessment of product quality increases, the more judgments on purchasing decisions will increase.

Table 6. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results on Price and Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	24.375	4.381		5.564	.000
	Price (X1)	-.208	.092	-.276	-2.268	.026
	Product Quality (X2)	.190	.071	.326	2.682	.009

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decisions (Y)

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Based on the results of the multiple linear equations, it shows that the price variable (X1) and product quality (X2) have a positive influence on purchasing decisions (Y). The price variable has an influence on purchasing decisions with a maximum beta value of -0.276 or -27.6%. While the product quality variable has an influence on purchasing decisions with a value of 0.326 or 32.6%. The explanation above shows that product quality has more influence than the price variable in purchasing decisions. The results of this data provide the possibility that in increasing consumer purchasing decisions by improving product quality first, then followed by price affordability and price suitability with product quality. The better the quality of the product and the affordability of the price, the purchasing decision will increase.

Table 7. Results of Significance Test of Price and Product Quality on Purchasing Decisions

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	232.972	2	116.486	21.066	.000 ^b
	Residual	519.770	94	5.529		
	Total	752.742	96			

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decisions (Y)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Product Quality (X2), Price (X1)

The results showed that the calculated F value > F table or 21.066 > 3.092 with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05, then H0 was rejected and Ha was accepted. From the data above, it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is that price and product quality simultaneously influence purchasing decisions.

VI. DISCUSSIONS

Based on the research that has been done, the first hypothesis states that there is an effect of the price variable on purchasing decisions stating that price has a negative effect on purchasing decisions is proven. This is proven through simple regression calculations where $Y = 35.700 + -0.382 X1$, which means that prices have a negative effect on purchasing decisions. While the correlation coefficient (r) or the closeness between the price variable (X1) and the purchase decision (Y) is -0.507, so this shows that there is a relationship between the price variable and the purchase decision at intervals of 0.400-0.599 which means strong. Next, the result of the determination test for the price variable (X1) on the purchase decision (Y) is 0.257 (R Square), so that it can be interpreted that 23.0% of the purchase decision variable (Y) can be explained by the price variable (X1). In addition, the result of the t-value of -5,727 is greater than the t-table value of 1.661 and the significance value obtained is 0.00 < 0.05 which shows H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. So it can be concluded that the price variable has influence and has a negative and significant relationship to the purchasing decision variable. The explanation above is proof that hypothesis 1 with the statement "price has a negative effect on purchasing decisions" is accepted. The first finding is regarding the price variable that has a negative and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Before making a purchase, consumers consider the price because price is one of the sacrifices consumers make to get the product. Price variables include price affordability, suitability of price with quality, quantity and product benefits obtained, and price competitiveness by comparing with other similar products. Efforts regarding price compatibility create incentives that generate consumer interest in the product to be purchased so that it can increase purchasing decisions. This hypothesis is in accordance with previous research from Waseso Segoro and Debi Nurlita, (2021) which showed that the high purchasing decisions made by consumers were due, in part, to the influence of the price of J.Co Donuts & Coffee products in Tangerang City. The perceptions of respondents in this study who gave a high value to the price variable argued that price affordability, price compatibility with product quality, price competitiveness and price compatibility with the benefits provided were factors in purchasing decisions.

The second hypothesis states that there is an influence of product quality variables on purchasing decisions, stating that product quality has an effect on purchasing decisions. This is proven through simple regression calculations where $Y = 15.759 + 0.303 X1$, which means that product quality has a positive effect on purchasing decisions. The correlation coefficient (r) or the closeness between product quality variables (X2) and purchasing decisions (Y) is 0.521. The results of the correlation coefficient test show that the relationship between product quality variables (X2) and purchasing decisions (Y) is positive and significant. If you look at the r value interval table, the value of 0.521 is in the interval 0.400-0.599 which means the level of correlation is sufficient. While the results of the product quality variable determination test (X2) on purchasing decisions (Y) are 0.272 (R Square).

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So it can be seen that 27.2% of the purchasing decision variable (Y) can be explained by the product quality variable (X2). Furthermore, the value of t count is 5.953 greater than t table 1.661 and the significance value obtained is $0.00 < 0.05$ which shows H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. So it can be concluded that the product quality variable has a significant influence and relationship to the purchasing decision variable. The explanation above is proof that hypothesis 2 in the form of "price has a positive effect on purchasing decisions" is accepted. The second finding is regarding product quality variables that have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Before making a purchase, consumers consider the quality of the product to be obtained. The research described above is in accordance with the research of Angraini and Harwani (2020), which shows that the high purchasing decisions made by consumers are due, in part, to the positive and significant influence on the quality of Sari Roti products in the city of West Jakarta. Respondents' perceptions in this study were that the purchase decision variable gave a high score in the opinion that performance, reliability, confirmation to specifications, surability, aesthetics, and perceived quality were given by the Tambi Black Tea Celup to be a factor in purchasing decisions.

The third hypothesis states that there is an effect of price and product quality on purchasing decisions, which states that price and product quality have an effect on purchasing decisions together. This is proven through multiple regression calculations, namely $Y = 22.726 + (-0.173X_1) + 0.212X_2$ which explains that price and product quality have a joint effect on purchasing decisions. While the value of the correlation coefficient between the price variable (X1) and the product quality variable (X2) on the purchase decision variable (Y) is 0.556. With the correlation coefficient at the interval of 0.400 -0.599, it can be concluded that the correlation is sufficient. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination is 0.309, so that 30.9% of the purchasing decision variable (Y) can be explained by the price variable (X1) and product quality variable (X2). Furthermore, the calculated F value is 3.092 with a table F value of 3.092. So that the value of F count $>$ F table or $21,066 > 3.092$ with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. From the data above it can be concluded that the 3rd hypothesis "allegedly there is an effect of price and product quality on purchasing decisions" is accepted. The third finding regarding price and product quality variables that jointly influence purchasing decisions is in accordance with research conducted by Segoro and Muliando (2020) which shows that the high purchasing decisions made by consumers are due, in part, to the influence of the quality of Michelle's bread products in Depok City Margonda. Respondents' perceptions in this study on purchasing decision variables that give high scores argue that performance, reliability, confirmation to specifications, surability, aesthetics, and perceived quality are given by the Black Tea Celup Tambi to be factors in purchasing decisions.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

1. Based on this research, it can be seen that the results of the independent variable, namely price (X1), have a significant and partial negative effect on the dependent variable, namely purchasing decisions (Y) for consumers of Tambi Black Tea Dip PT Perkebunan Tambi Wonosobo. Overall, prices can encourage consumers to make purchasing decisions for Black Tea Dip Tambi, where if the price drops, the purchase decision will increase or vice versa.
2. Based on this research, it can be seen that the results of the independent variable, namely product quality (X2), have a significant and partial positive effect on the dependent variable, namely purchasing decisions (Y) for consumers of Tambi Black Tea Dip PT Perkebunan Tambi Wonosobo. Overall, product quality can encourage consumers to make purchasing decisions for Black Tea Dip Tambi where if product quality increases, purchasing decisions will also increase.
3. Based on this research, it can be seen that the independent variables namely price (X1) and product quality variables (X2) simultaneously have a significant influence on the dependent variable, namely purchasing decisions (Y) for consumers of Tambi Black Tea Dip PT Perkebunan Tambi Wonosobo. Overall, the price and quality of the product can encourage consumers to make a purchasing decision for Tambi Black Tea.

VIII. SUGGESTION

1. In the price variable, there are factors that still score below the average from consumers, namely price competitiveness, where according to some consumers other similar products are cheaper and more affordable. Referring to that, it is necessary to pay attention to the price competitiveness factor because in this study it received the lowest rating from the respondents. Efforts that can be made to overcome this problem, PT Perkebunan Tambi need to evaluate the pricing of the Tambi Black Tea Bag by looking at the pricing of other similar products so that consumers do not switch to other brands. Increasing the factor of price competitiveness and suitability of prices with benefits has an effect on increasing purchasing decisions.
2. In the product quality variable, there are several factors that still score below the average from consumers, namely regarding the beauty of the packaging and the procedure for serving it. According to some respondents, the product packaging and color did not attract attention and some respondents ignored the serving instructions so that the tea was not served

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optimally. Referring to that, the Tambi Black Tea Bag needs to simplify the presentation procedures that are easy to understand either through pictures or writing that raises consumer interest to follow. Apart from that, the company should try to evaluate the packaging design and increase the uniqueness of the packaging by holding a product packaging design competition and the most attractive one will be selected as the winner and then the design will be applied as PT Perkebunan Tambi's product packaging so that the packaging can generate consumer interest. Increasing the ease of presentation and beauty of packaging factors can improve purchasing decisions.

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